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DE-RISK Project

D2.4: Lessons learned and best practices based on the customer behavior change journey

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Abbreviations and Acronyms	
AVE	Average variance extracted
CR	Composite reliability
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
LFM	Local Flexibility Market
M	Month
p	P-value
PLS	Partial least squares
SEM	Structural equation modelling
ST	Sustainable technologies
T	Task
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable was developed by Universidade NOVA de Lisboa (UNL) – NOVA Information Management School within the scope of Work Package 2 (WP2) of the Horizon Europe Project DE-RISK — DE-RISK the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems, which focused on understanding and enhancing citizen engagement in local flexibility markets (LFMs). It builds on prior efforts from Task 2.1, where the literature review and the initial research model and survey instruments were designed, and continues through Task 2.2, which involved multi-country data collection and quantitative testing using structural equation modeling techniques. Additionally, it integrates findings from Task 2.3, which provided engagement insights based on the empirical data. Together, these efforts culminate in a comprehensive view of the consumer behavior change journey in LFMs, offering both theoretical clarity and practical relevance.

The deliverable not only outlines the research concepts and methodological steps in detail but also presents the main behavioral insights and key limitations encountered throughout the analysis. It includes a longitudinal dimension to assess changes in user engagement over time. The outcome is a structured and data-driven framework designed to improve understanding of how citizens can be engaged in LFMs and similar energy initiatives. This framework is tailored for ease of interpretation and adaptation across different regional or technological contexts.

Designed as both a reference document and a practical toolkit, its replicable methodology and evidence-based insights are intended to guide stakeholders, including community organizers, developers, and policymakers, in crafting more inclusive and scalable engagement strategies. Ultimately, the recommendations derived from this work offer a strategic foundation for ensuring that LFMs are not only technologically viable but also socially embedded and behaviorally aligned with community needs, enabling a smoother and more participatory energy transition across Europe.

A. INTRODUCTION

Scope of the deliverable

As Europe accelerates its transition toward a decarbonized and decentralized energy system, local flexibility markets (LFMs) have emerged as a basis for balancing electricity supply and demand at the community level (Viadere, 2025). However, the effectiveness of these markets hinges not only on technological readiness or regulatory support, but fundamentally on the active participation and behavioral alignment of citizens and end-users (International energy agency, 2023; Neves, Oliveira, & Santini, 2024; Wang et al., 2022).

This deliverable presents a structured synthesis of the consumer behavior change journey within the context of LFMs, drawing on multivariate research that spans literature analysis, stakeholder interviews, and large-scale citizen surveys. The main objective is to extract actionable insights and mainly the best practices and adopted methodology in Work Package 2 for scaling up user engagement in LFMs, or similar types of initiatives. Beyond the citizens themselves, the report also considers the pivotal role of other stakeholders in the LFM ecosystem.

The findings presented here are intended not only for academic or evaluative purposes, but as a **practical guide for future deployments of LFMs**. The behavioral insights, validated through robust quantitative and qualitative analysis, offer a foundation for designing user-centric energy programs that are inclusive, scalable, and responsive to community values. Ultimately, this deliverable aims share the main lessons learned and best practices to ensure scalability and replicability of the engagement insights.

Objectives

The main goals of the current task are to:

- **Objective 1:** Provide a definition of the consumer behavior journey and its relevance in the context of energy initiatives;
- **Objective 2:** Share a step-by-step guide on the methodologies applied to replicate the consumer behavior analysis;

- **Objective 3:** Provide main engagement insights, including an additional study on engagement over time;
- **Objective 4:** Share lessons learned and outline a detailed framework of consumer engagement in LFMs to facilitate replicability processes.

Structure

The document is structured as follows. **Section B** presents a description of the customer behavior journey. **Section C** describes the step-by-step methodology to conduct a customer behavior analysis. **Section D** presents the main engagement insights resulting from the tasks of Work Package 2, followed by an additional study on engagement over time in **Section E**. **Section F** presents the lessons learned and the replicability framework. Finally, **Section G** presents the limitations of this analysis and framework, together with the conclusions in **Section H**.

B. DEFINITION OF CUSTOMER BEHAVIOR JOURNEY

Local flexibility markets (LFMs) refer to platforms for trading electrical flexibility at the distribution system operator (DSO) level, typically within confined geographic areas such as neighborhoods, communities, towns, or small cities (Antal et al., 2021; Jin et al., 2020). Within these markets, energy communities can act as key providers of flexibility. To participate, citizens often adopt sustainable technologies such as renewable energy systems, electric vehicles, smart meters, and intelligent thermostats. Through these tools, consumers can actively contribute to grid management by adjusting or shifting their electricity consumption in response to dynamic pricing signals or other financial incentives (Neves, Oliveira, & Sarker, 2024). As a result, the success of LFMs heavily depends on the willingness and engagement of citizens to take part in such programs. Therefore, the participation of citizens can be described as a behavioral process influenced by various psychological, social, and contextual factors. Understanding these factors becomes crucial to ensure a successful energy community.

Drawing inspiration from marketing, behavioral economics, and user experience design, the consumer journey framework helps identify critical stages in engagement and the factors that encourage or hinder progression through these stages. Viewing engagement as a journey rather than a binary choice allows for more targeted interventions and effective program design. The consumer behavior journey framework reveals not only whether people participate but how and why they choose to engage, disengage, or deepen their involvement. The consumer behavior journey maps the stages a person moves through in their interaction with a service or product. For this study, the model is applied to local flexibility markets, capturing how consumers become aware of, evaluate, join, and perceive the impact of their participation in energy community programs.

Going back to literature, one of the most well-known behavior journey models is AIDA (Awareness, Interest, Desire, Action). Originally from marketing, the AIDA model was introduced in 1898, and described four main stages consumers go through when engaging with a product or service: Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action. This model is commonly used to evaluate purchasing behavior, engagement of services, technology adoption, among others, since it tracks the psychological journey from awareness to purchase (Hassan et al., 2015). While the model has been adapted over time, its core principle, that consumers must first notice a product, develop interest, feel desire, and then take action, remains applicable, even in the digital era.

Figure 1 presents the AIDA model and a description of his four elements.

Figure 1. AIDA model

One of the main advantages of the AIDA model is that it can be tailored to several different contexts (e.g. Pawar & Islam, 2025; Song et al., 2021), including flexibility markets. Therefore, the consumer behavior journey on LFMs can also be described as a step-by-step pathway, starting with:

- (1) Awareness & Interest – by providing information about LFMs;
- (2) Desire – by understanding the citizens' motivations and concerns;
- (3) Action – usually triggered when stakeholders are able to prove how LFMs can answer to identified citizens' needs and meet their motivations and solve their barriers.

Consumers' decisions across the journey are shaped by several internal motivations and external factors (Neves et al., 2023). In fact, people often rely on heuristics or follow social norms, but real-world behavior does not follow a strict linear path. Taking actions and decisions based solely on theory or prior experience might not be enough, especially in situations where the behavior is still new – like the participation in local flexibility markets.

Therefore, developing a consumer behavior analysis provides:

- Actionable insights for tailoring support.
- Improved design of consumer interfaces.
- Greater engagement through understanding and tackling barriers and concerns.

In the context of local flexibility markets, this framing helps bridge the gap between technical solutions and human behavior.

C. STEP-BY-STEP METHODOLOGY

Understanding consumer participation in local flexibility markets requires a multivariate approach. This chapter defines comprehensively the adopted methodology to analyze consumer behavior, making use of a mixed-methods research strategy spanning qualitative and quantitative methodologies.

The methodology comprises the following seven integrated stages:

1. Literature Review
2. Qualitative Stakeholder Analysis
3. Development of a Research Model
4. Quantitative Survey and Sampling Strategy
5. Data collection
6. Model Validation using Structural Equation Modelling
7. Development of recommendations based on the results of step 6

Each component plays a strategic role in identifying, confirming, and testing variables that influence consumer decisions regarding participation in LFMs. Figure 2 describes the main steps taken to perform the consumer behavior analysis.

Figure 2. Methodological steps

1. Literature Review

Types of literature review

The first step of the consumer behavior journey analysis is a literature review. The main objective is to identify the main factors influencing consumers' decisions regarding local flexibility markets, or similar initiatives, that have been explored in prior research. Different **types of literature reviews** exist serving varied purposes:

- **Narrative Reviews:** This type of literature review is usually more broad, subjective and unstructured. It is often learned as one of the first ways to conduct literature review and is a more general approach. There is no predetermined research question or specified search strategy, only a topic of interest, following no specific protocol. It therefore gives a general understanding of the topic, but usually more superficial and not in depth;
- **Systematic Reviews:** This type of review is much more rigorous as it involves inclusion/exclusion criteria and replicable methodologies. It identifies, collects and analyses available research outputs through a systematic process. The main objective is to review critical areas on the topic, understand the current state of the art and evolution of the phenomenon, as well as suggesting topics for further research (Carrera-Rivera et al., 2022);
- **Meta-Analyses:** A meta-analysis synthesizes past research in a more statistical way. It proceeds to a statistical aggregation of results from multiple studies to establish effect sizes. It is often seen as a more robust method since it exposes the main relationships and possible gaps. It provides a pooled effect size of the variables found in literature, being able to distinguish the most statistically significant relationships found (Neves et al., 2022). It therefore has the drawback of only relying on quantitative studies;
- **Weight Analyses:** The weight analysis is often considered as a complementary method to the meta analysis. It is basically the assessment of the frequency and consistency of variable significance across studies. It allows identifying the most frequently used variables and categorizing them as “best” and “promising” indicators (Jeyaraj et al., 2006).

In the specific topic of LFM and similar types of initiatives, a hybrid approach was chosen, using a meta-analysis, and weight analysis. Since the main objective was to identify and add relevant variables to the consumer research model, a literature review that could identify and quantify the importance of those factors tested in past research was found to be the most suitable.

Selection process

After choosing the method of literature review, it is relevant to choose how to **select the relevant studies**. Therefore, a database search is conducted, usually across Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. A set of keywords is selected, and queries are performed. For example, some of the followings were used: "energy communities", "local flexibility markets", "consumer participation" and "citizen acceptance". Once the articles are identified, a set of criteria should be developed, taking into consideration the timeframe, the type of articles, the context of research, and data availability. The inclusion criteria specifically for the conducted study included peer-reviewed studies from 2010 to 2024, empirical focus, relevance to European and global LFM contexts, reporting sample sizes and correlation effects, for the meta analysis purposes. Figure 3 summarizes the selection process.

Figure 3. Selection process

Coding and statistical analysis

Once the identification and selection process is concluded, in the case of meta and weight analysis, coding and merging of variables is relevant, as variables sometimes present different names but with the same meaning. Sample sizes and correlation effects are collected, together with the information about the journal, year of publication and geographical context. Based on this, a descriptive analysis is performed to identify the most published journals, the regions with more studies, and the evolution of the topic. With the coefficients, the meta analysis is performed, being able to get a pooled coefficient for each relationship and evaluating their statistical significance. This was performed with R software. Finally, a literature model is presented, showing the most studied relationships in literature, together with their size effect (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Literature review model

This model will be the starting point to build the consumer research model presented in the next steps.

2. Qualitative Study

The next step in the methodology is to conduct an exploratory qualitative research. The **main objectives** of this study are to:

- Validate literature-derived variables in real-world settings.
- Identify additional context-specific factors.
- Explore stakeholder perceptions and language.

Sampling and Participants

Regarding the **sampling strategy**, both purposive/convenience or random samples are valid. Very often, due to constraints on the topic or difficulty of finding interviewees, a convenient sampling approach is selected. In this part, it is extremely relevant to identify the type of stakeholders from which it is important to get input. Specifically to LFMs, both a set of consumers and experts were relevant to get two different perspectives on the phenomenon. This is aligned with the choices conducted in prior and similar research (Neves & Oliveira, 2023; Wunderlich et al., 2019). Specifically to the DE-RISK project, 14 interviews were conducted across the pilot regions. Table 1 presents the interviewees' details.

Table 1. Interviews characteristics

Interviewee	Country	Type
1	France	Expert
2	France	Consumer
3	Portugal	Expert
4	Portugal	Expert
5	Portugal	Consumer
6	Portugal	Consumer
7	Portugal	Consumer
8	Spain	Expert
9	Spain	Expert
10	Spain	Consumer
11	Spain	Consumer
12	Turkey	Expert
13	Turkey	Consumer
14	Turkey	Consumer

Before conducting the interview, a **semi-structured interview** guide should be developed. It is important to note that an informed consent should also be developed to comply with the project ethical requirements. Interviews usually have a duration of 30 to 60 minutes, and the number of interviews should be based on data saturation. Data saturation refers to a situation where one can't take any new information from the collected data (Fusch & Ness, 2015). Additionally, specifically to the topic of LFMs, an introductory video explaining the concept was produced and shown before every interview, guaranteeing that interviewees had the same or a minimum understanding of the topic.

Qualitative analysis

After collecting the qualitative data (transcription of interviews), several methods can be used to analyse data, including open coding methodology, thematic analysis, among others. **Open coding methodology** is usually applied in an initial stage, where data is broken down into smaller segments and labeled with descriptive codes. Thematic analysis, on the other hand, is a method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within the topics extracted from the qualitative data.

In the DE-RISK project, an open coding methodology was adopted, following the suggestion of prior research (Wunderlich et al., 2019). This approach is described in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Open coding methodology

The **open coding methodology** can be broken down into the following steps:

1. Familiarization with the data – transcribe interviews and add interviewer notes when needed;
2. Generation of initial codes – generate codes from the interviews together with statement of each interviewee supporting such codes;

3. Merging and reviewing themes – merge codes with similar meanings and review all codes;
4. Defining and naming themes – choose only the most referred codes and name them based on literature;
5. Cross validation and triangulation with variables existing in literature – find similar variables already used in literature (if possible), since their scale of measurement was already validated;
6. Adding variables to the research model.

3. Model Development

The third step of the methodology is to build the consumer behavior model. This model integrates the findings from both literature review and qualitative study. Sometimes it also includes variables/factors that are essential to be evaluated from the project's KPIs. Figure 6 presents a scheme of the consumer behavior model development.

Figure 6. Consumer behavior model development

The consumer research model should have clearly identified the explanatory and target variables, as well as some already established hypothesis, i.e., the expected impact of each dimension on the target behaviors. Finally, some control variables should also be added to the model. Control variables are factors that are kept constant or limited to prevent them

from influencing the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Usually they are composed of socio-demographic data, like age, gender and country of analysis (Ferreira et al., 2023). These variables will be the basis for the questionnaire.

4. Questionnaire development

The **questionnaire design** formed a foundational component of the research methodology, consisting of items/questions distributed across approximately 25 constructs. These constructs were carefully chosen and adapted from literature. The questionnaire was first developed in English, and later translated into the languages of each country in which data was collected (pilot countries). The reverse process was also conducted to ensure that questions had the same meaning across all languages (Cha et al., 2007). Prior to full deployment, the instrument was pretested to ensure both clarity and reliability, reducing the likelihood of misinterpretation and improving the consistency of responses across diverse demographic groups. The survey was delivered through online platforms and with the help of a market research company.

To further enhance comprehension and mitigate disparities in participants' baseline knowledge, a short, **one-minute explainer video** was developed and disseminated alongside the survey. This video provided a concise yet comprehensive overview of Local Flexibility Markets (LFMs), ensuring that all participants, regardless of prior exposure, shared a common understanding of the key concepts being studied. By addressing knowledge asymmetries upfront, the video helped standardize the respondents' frame of reference, thereby strengthening the internal validity of the questionnaire responses. This innovative step in survey administration played a critical role in ensuring the robustness and inclusiveness of the data collection process.

5. Data collection

The data collection process followed a **probabilistic sampling approach** to ensure the representativeness and statistical validity of the findings. Using the standard market research sample size formula:

$$n = (Z^2 \times p \times (1 - p)) / e^2$$

We established the minimum required sample size per region. Applying a 95% confidence level ($Z = 1.96$), a pessimistic/conservative proportion estimate ($p = 0.5$), and a 5% margin of error ($e = 0.05$), the resulting minimum sample size was 384 respondents for each region with a population exceeding 10 000 (which we believe it's the case in all countries). This approach ensured that the sample could accurately reflect broader population trends. The final dataset comprised around 2 000 valid responses collected across five participating project sites, providing therefore a robust base for the subsequent statistical analysis and modelling.

The **target population** consisted of individuals aged 18 and older who were either solely responsible or jointly responsible for energy-related decisions in their households, including the adoption of new energy technologies. To enhance comparability across countries and demographic groups, quotas were applied to balance age and gender distribution within each national sample. These quotas were designed to mirror the demographic profile of each country's adult population, thereby improving the generalizability of the results. This careful calibration of the sampling and data collection process helped ensure that the insights derived from the study would be both representative and actionable for policy makers, energy planners, and community organizations. Tables 2 and 3 present the age and gender quotas per country.

Table 2. Age quotas

Age	Turkey	Spain	France	Ireland	Portugal
<=24	37%	24%	30%	33%	24%
25-49	37%	35%	31%	36%	33%
50-64	16%	21%	19%	17%	21%
>=65	10%	20%	21%	15%	22%

Table 3. Gender quotas

Gender	Turkey	Spain	France	Ireland	Portugal
Male	50%	49%	48%	50%	47%
Female	50%	51%	52%	50%	53%

6. Statistical analysis: Structural equation modelling (SEM)

To perform the statistical analysis of data, several methods can be chosen. Various methods can be used to perform statistical data analysis. However, given the need for a predictive approach capable of capturing multiple effects and handling multiple target variables simultaneously, structural equation modeling (SEM) is an appropriate choice. **Structural equation modelling (SEM)** is an advanced multivariate statistical technique used to analyze complex relationships between observed and latent variables (J. Hair et al., 2018). Unlike traditional regression methods, SEM allows researchers to simultaneously estimate multiple relationships, incorporating both direct and indirect effects among variables. It is especially useful for modelling constructs that cannot be directly observed, by using multiple items as indicators for these latent variables. In this sense, SEM enables a more holistic understanding of behavioral phenomena.

In the context of this study, SEM was applied to examine the factors influencing citizens' intention to participate in local flexibility markets. The method allowed for the integration of psychological, social, financial, and motivational dimensions into a single model, highlighting both the strength and significance of each factor's impact. Two main techniques exist on SEM: **covariance-based (CB-SEM)** and **variance-based (PLS-SEM)**. Table 4 provides a comparison between covariance and variance-based methods.

Table 4. Covariance based VS Variance based methods

Feature	CB-SEM	PLS-SEM
Goal	Confirm theoretical models	Predict and explore relationships
Sample Size	Large (n > 500)	Medium to small (n > 150)
Assumptions	Normality, linearity	Flexible
Output	Model fit indices	Path coefficients, R ²

Specifically, the partial least squares SEM (PLS-SEM) approach was used via SmartPLS, which is particularly suitable for exploratory research and theory development when constructs are still being defined or when the goal is to maximize the explained variance. This approach provided insights into which variables most strongly drive participation intentions, offering a robust basis for practical engagement strategies. The software SMART PLS 4.0 was used to conduct the analysis (Ringle, 2022).

Key outputs

Regarding the main outputs of SMART PLS, they are divided into two main components: the measurement model and the structural model. The **measurement model** evaluates how well the observed indicators (survey items) reflect their corresponding latent constructs. This involves assessing indicator reliability, internal consistency (e.g., composite reliability), and convergent and discriminant validity (e.g., average variance extracted, Fornell-Larcker criterion, HTMT, loadings and cross loadings). Once the measurement model is validated, the **structural model** examines the hypothesized relationships between constructs. This includes the estimation of path coefficients (indicating the strength and direction of relationships) and R^2 values (indicating the explained variance in the dependent variables). Multicollinearity should also be assessed, usually using the variance inflation factor (VIF) (Fornell & Bookstein, 1982; Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2011; Henseler et al., 2015). Together, these outputs allow researchers to confirm the theoretical structure of the model, identify the most influential factors, and assess how well the model predicts citizens' behaviors. If needed, an analysis per country should also be performed to provide a cross-country comparison and testing the robustness of the results.

7. Development of recommendations

The final step of the methodological process involved translating the insights from the PLS-SEM analysis into actionable recommendations for enhancing consumer engagement. The model results identified key drivers of participation, direct or indirectly. These findings should support targeted strategies for LFM implementation and user engagement, mainly focusing on:

- Communication strategies
- Program/technology design
- Policy recommendations

Overall, this methodological framework provides a **replicable and evidence-based roadmap** for understanding and enhancing consumer participation in decentralized energy initiatives. It offers:

- A strong theoretical foundation grounded in behavior change and community engagement theories.
- A practice-oriented approach, integrating input from stakeholders and citizens.
- Quantitative rigor through advanced statistical modelling.

Together, these components make the framework both academically robust and practically relevant, offering a solid base for the formulation of strategic actions and the replication of successful models across diverse contexts. The following chapters will elaborate on these recommendations and present a set of consolidated **lessons learned** to guide future LFM design and implementation efforts.

D. MAIN ENGAGEMENT INSIGHTS

This section synthesizes the key behavioral insights derived from the multi-country study on citizens' engagement in local flexibility markets, performed under WP2. It builds upon both qualitative and quantitative findings, presenting the underlying motivations and barriers that shape individuals' decisions to participate. The objective is to translate these findings into initial engagement strategies, laying the groundwork for exploitation and replication activities.

The behavioral model tested in this study incorporated constructs from four foundational psychological and sociological theories: Protection Motivation Theory (PMT), Social Identity Theory (SIT), Empowerment Theory, and hedonic/instrumental motivation literature. This model was further enriched by qualitative insights and financial perception variables identified during stakeholder consultations. These dimensions were tested across five countries, generating robust and context-sensitive conclusions. Next sub-sections present the main insights.

Protection Motivation Theory: Emphasize Copying, Not Threating

From the PMT framework, self-efficacy emerged as the only coping-related factor with a statistically significant positive impact on intention to participate. In contrast, threat-related variables, such as perceived vulnerability or severity of environmental threats, were not found to influence behavioral intention meaningfully. This suggests that **empowering communication strategies, those that reinforce citizens' ability to act, are far more effective than fear-based messaging**. Citizens respond more favorably when they are presented as capable change agents, rather than as passive victims of climate risk.

Implications:

- Develop materials that highlight achievable individual and community-level actions.
- Use narratives and testimonials that showcase citizen agency.
- Avoid overemphasis on climate urgency without pathways for personal contribution.

Social Identity Theory: Commitment and Shared Purpose

From the social identity dimension, community identification, shared values, and commitment all showed a significant positive effect on participation intention, with commitment being particularly influential. Surprisingly, community trust did not appear significant, suggesting that people assume basic trustworthiness within their community or do not view LFM as vulnerable to internal sabotage.

Implications:

- Engagement strategies should strengthen a collective mission—particularly around sustainability or local economic benefit.
- Pre-engagement activities such as community workshops, clean energy days, or local green festivals can foster shared purpose.
- Visual identity tools (e.g. logos, slogans, or local ambassadors) may enhance emotional attachment and participation.

Hedonic Motivation and Perceived Usefulness: Design for Enjoyment

Contrary to expectations, **hedonic motivations**, i.e. the enjoyment, fun, or satisfaction gained from participating had a stronger influence than perceived usefulness. This highlights the importance of emotional engagement and experiential design in energy initiatives.

Implications:

- Implement gamified interfaces with feedback, points, leaderboards, or badges.
- Use storytelling and visualization tools to make progress in LFM engaging and tangible.
- Frame activities as social or rewarding, rather than purely functional or administrative.

Financial Considerations: Control and Incentives

Financial factors presented a dual pattern, as (1) **loss of control over spending** (e.g. unexpected energy bills or complex pricing) negatively impacted participation; (2) **discount programs** had a strong positive effect across several countries. This indicates that while financial benefits are important, what citizens value more is clarity and predictability, rather than abstract savings.

Implications:

- Communicate clearly about potential costs and savings using visual bill simulations or real-case scenarios.
- Offer opt-in discount schemes, loyalty rewards, or shared-benefit structures.
- Enhance financial literacy through short video explainers or interactive budgeting tools.

Empowerment: The Most Critical Factor

Empowerment emerged as the **most influential factor** on participation intention and acted as a moderator between participation and perceived wellbeing. The four psychological dimensions of empowerment—competence, meaning, impact, and self-determination—are thus vital levers for LFM engagement.

Implications:

- Foster transparency and autonomy in community decision-making.
- Provide interactive dashboards for monitoring energy contributions and benefits.
- Use gamification to allow citizens to track personal achievements and milestones.
- Invest in workshops, forums, and co-design activities that let citizens shape the LFM roadmap.

Cross-Country Patterns and Cultural Differences

Regarding country results, the following was achieved:

- **Empowerment** was universally the top predictor across all five countries.
- **Self-efficacy** stood out in Portugal, Ireland, and Türkiye, suggesting personal confidence in climate action is a cultural asset in these contexts.
- **Discount programs** had the greatest impact in France, Portugal, and Ireland, underscoring cost-sensitivity in these countries.
- **Community-related variables** were stronger in Spain, France, and Türkiye, indicating a more collectivist orientation.
- **Hedonic motivation** was uniquely significant in Spain, emphasizing the role of enjoyable engagement formats.

E. ENGAGEMENT OVER TIME

To complement the cross-sectional behavioral modelling, a longitudinal study was conducted to assess how technology can support participation in local flexibility markets and how such participation, over time, contributes to broader community and individual outcomes. The longitudinal design allowed for tracking outcomes at a second time point (T2), enabling stronger interpretations of the relationships between technology use, participation, and impact.

A **longitudinal study** is a research design that involves collecting data from the same subjects at multiple points in time. Unlike cross-sectional studies, which provide a snapshot of a phenomenon at one moment, longitudinal studies track changes, developments, or outcomes over time. This design is particularly valuable in behavioral and social sciences because it allows researchers to observe trends, causal relationships, and long-term effects (Ballinger, 2004). Measuring the outcomes of a behavior in a second moment of time is critical for several reasons:

- 1. Capturing lasting impact:** Immediate behavior (e.g., signing up for an energy initiative) doesn't always translate to long-term engagement. By measuring outcomes later, we can see whether intentions lead to sustained behavior, satisfaction, or benefits.
- 2. Understanding causality:** Longitudinal data helps disentangle cause and effect. For instance, if participation in a local energy initiative leads to increased empowerment or wellbeing over time, this can be more confidently asserted with data from multiple time points.
- 3. Identifying behavior change trajectories:** Some effects like trust-building, habit formation, or empowerment take time to develop. Measuring only at a single point risks missing these critical dynamics.

In summary, longitudinal research provides a richer, more accurate understanding of how interventions unfold, evolve, and sustain impact over time, essential for designing effective, scalable, and lasting behavior change programs. This is even more relevant when trying to measure outcomes of a behavior, which was the main objective of this second study.

This follow-up study focused on the dynamic relationships across three core dimensions:

1. **Technology engagement** (frequency and diversity of platform use),
2. **LEC participation**, and
3. **Community and individual outcomes** (measured at a second moment of time).

Figure 7 (see image below) summarizes the model and its relationships. Technology is explored both in usage frequency and diversity. Regarding outcomes, both community and individual outcomes were evaluated, namely, community environmental performance, energy poverty alleviation and perceived well-being. Finally, age, gender, income and country were used as control variables. The questionnaire is presented on Appendix A.

Figure 7. Longitudinal research model

Data analysis and results

To test the research model, the same individuals from the first data collection were questioned. A total of 124 complete responses were collected. It is important to notice that two years passed between the first (2023) and second (2025) data collection. Therefore, the reduction in the number of responses was expected.

Regarding the data analysis, once more the partial least squares was the chosen method. This method first requires an assessment of the measurement model and later the structural model. The next sub-sections present all criteria.

Measurement model

First, the reliability of constructs is validated by the means of composite reliability (CR), that should be greater than 0.7, and average variance extracted (AVE), that should present values greater than 0.5. As shown in Table 5, both criteria are met, establishing reliability and validity of the constructs (J. Hair et al., 2016).

Table 5. Composite reliability (CR); Fornell-Lacker criteria (the diagonal values are the square root of AVE)

	CR	UB	CEP	EPA	LEC	PWLEC
Frequency of use (UB)	0.982	0.974				
Community environmental performance (CEP)	0.953	0.596	0.914			
Energy poverty alleviation (EPA)	0.951	0.521	0.826	0.910		
Participation LEC (LEC)	0.989	0.711	0.534	0.512	0.983	
Perceived well-being (PWLEC)	0.988	0.702	0.654	0.578	0.697	0.977

The second step is to evaluate discriminant validity. For this, three criteria are used: (1) Fornell-Larcker criteria, which establishes that the correlation between constructs should always be smaller than the square root of the average variance extracted of each construct (see Table 5) (Fornell & Bookstein, 1982); (2) Heterotrait-monotrait ratio, which should present values below 0.9, as confirmed in Table 6 (Henseler et al., 2015); (3) a comparison of loadings and cross loadings, in which the first should always be greater than the second mentioned (see Table 7). As presented, all criteria are met, therefore establishing discriminant validity among the constructs (J. Hair et al., 2014). This means that the structural model can be evaluated.

Table 6. Heterotrait-monotrait ratio

	UB	CEP	EPA	LEC	PWLEC
Frequency of use (UB)					
Community environmental performance (CEP)	0.623				
Energy poverty alleviation (EPA)	0.542	0.879			
Participation LEC (LEC)	0.727	0.556	0.529		
Perceived well-being (PWLEC)	0.717	0.682	0.596	0.708	

Table 7. Loadings and cross-loadings

	LEC	UB	CEP	EPA	PWLEC
LEC1	0.977	0.697	0.519	0.501	0.672
LEC2	0.990	0.709	0.532	0.507	0.698
LEC3	0.983	0.693	0.524	0.501	0.684
UB1	0.674	0.960	0.549	0.482	0.671
UB2	0.711	0.983	0.595	0.525	0.692
UB3	0.692	0.978	0.597	0.514	0.689
CEP1	0.438	0.482	0.889	0.664	0.576
CEP2	0.502	0.590	0.931	0.769	0.628
CEP3	0.507	0.578	0.927	0.781	0.554
CEP4	0.501	0.522	0.906	0.796	0.633
EPA1	0.548	0.521	0.813	0.908	0.611
EPA2	0.468	0.477	0.746	0.927	0.550
EPA3	0.442	0.481	0.741	0.911	0.498
EPA4	0.385	0.401	0.691	0.895	0.422
PWLEC1	0.672	0.673	0.631	0.564	0.962
PWLEC2	0.697	0.702	0.637	0.558	0.982
PWLEC3	0.688	0.701	0.663	0.582	0.981
PWLEC4	0.664	0.669	0.626	0.555	0.983

Regarding the formative construct - diversity of use -, the statistical significance of the weights and loadings of the items, as well as the multicollinearity was assessed. As shown in Table 8, all items have statistically significant loadings and variance inflation factor lower than 5, suggesting the suitability of the formative construct.

Table 8. Weights, loadings and VIF for formative construct

	Weights	Loadings	VIF
Diversity_of_use1	0.241*	0.694***	1.411
Diversity_of_use2	0.233	0.743***	1.702
Diversity_of_use3	0.183	0.763***	2.345
Diversity_of_use4	0.195	0.798***	2.436
Diversity_of_use5	0.406**	0.894***	2.294

Structural model

Before testing the structural model, the multicollinearity between constructs was assessed using the variance inflation factor (VIF). This criterion was below the threshold of 5, suggesting no multicollinearity issues. Therefore, the statistical significance of the path coefficients was assessed by the means of bootstrapping with 5 000 iterations. Figure 8 presents the structural model results.

Figure 8. Structural model results

Note: p-value < 0.01 ***; p-value < 0.05 **; p-value < 0.1 *

Results show that the model explains 57.4% of the variation in participation, and 45.7%, 37.8%, and 67.2% of the variation in community environmental performance, energy poverty alleviation and perceived well-being, respectively. Regarding the technology related variables, both are statistically significant in explaining the participation. However, only frequency of use positively impacts the outcomes, suggesting that frequency is more important than diversity of technologies available and used. Participation in LFM strongly influences all outcomes, nevertheless these relationships are moderated by the technology variables. As shown in Figure 9, the impact of participation on the perceived wellbeing is only positive (and strong) for people that frequently use sustainable technologies. This suggests the relevance of having a daily interaction with sustainable technologies to be informed and adapt consumption behaviors that will later translate into improved quality of life.

Figure 9. Moderation effect of frequency of use between participation and perceived well-being

Finally, Figure 10 shows the moderating effect of diversity of use in the relationship between participation and perceived well-being. As shown, the impact of participation in well-being is always positive, but is much stronger for lower levels of diversity of use. This suggests that having a diversified set of sustainable technologies can indeed support well-being when there is a low level of participation. However, it is not enough for high levels of participation. For example, for greater levels of participation, as shown in Figure 10, frequency of use becomes much more relevant.

Figure 10. Moderation effect of diversity of use between participation and perceived well-being

Key results

Based on the longitudinal results and the moderating effects of technology use, several practical and strategic recommendations emerge to enhance both citizen participation in LFM and their positive outcomes on community performance, wellbeing, and energy poverty alleviation:

- 1. Prioritize frequency of use over mere technology access** - Frequency of use has a stronger effect on outcomes than diversity of technologies. Even though not all sustainable technologies require a constant interaction, it is important for the consumer to be frequently engaged on those, receiving feedback and adapting behaviors accordingly. Some recommendations are:
 - Encourage regular, habitual interaction with sustainable technologies (e.g., daily energy monitoring, smart thermostat adjustments).
 - Design user-friendly interfaces and gamified engagement tools to nudge frequent use.
 - Provide reminders, tips, and feedback loops that make daily energy actions feel relevant and rewarding.
- 2. Support low-engagement users through diversified technologies** - Diversity of technology use compensates for lower participation, especially regarding perceived well-being. Therefore, some recommendations pass by:
 - Promoting bundled technology packages (e.g., PV + smart meter + battery) particularly for users less likely to engage deeply in the community.
 - Educating on how different technologies complement each other in daily life, even without active participation in LFM governance.
- 3. Rethink success metrics** - Participation alone is not a full indicator of outcome success, technology behavior and humanistic impacts matters too. Some recommendations are as follows:
 - Combine behavioral data (frequency, diversity) with engagement metrics in performance evaluations.
 - Define KPIs that reflect both community-level impacts and individual-level well-being gains.

In summary, findings point to a dual-path strategy: participation in LFM drives community outcomes broadly, but individual outcomes like well-being require frequent, meaningful interactions with sustainable technologies.

F. LESSONS LEARNED AND REPLICABILITY FRAMEWORK

This chapter consolidates the findings of our research into actionable lessons for the design, implementation, and sustainability of LFMs, from the consumer perspective. Drawing from the work developed on WP2, we outline a comprehensive engagement framework designed to help the replicability of the consumer behavior journey analysis, finalizing with four key lessons learned.

Replicability framework

In order to facilitate the replicability and scalability of the consumer behavior analysis, a framework was developed, comprising all steps, including methodological ones. The framework is divided into four main steps, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Replicability framework

The framework is composed of four main steps, namely:

- Step 1: Understand – Clarifying the Objective** – the first step is about defining the objective of the consumer behavior journey, asking the question “*which consumer behavior do we want to understand?*”. It is possible to select several behaviors too, since structural equation modelling allows for several target dimensions. Specifically to the DE-RISK project, the main objective was to understand which factors influence citizens’ decision to participate in LFMs and consequently use sustainable energy technologies. Additionally, the expected and perceived impact of that participation was also defined to be explored, both on more practical and humanistic outcomes. Therefore, three main focus areas emerged: (1) role of technology; (2) pathways to participation; and (3) outcomes.

- **Step 2: Analyze – Methodology Overview** – here we need to specify how we can achieve the objectives methodologically. A structured methodological plan should be developed. We recommend to start with (1) literature review; (2) exploratory qualitative study; and (3) quantitative study, therefore adopting a mixed-methods approach. Specifically to our project, the literature review conducted was a meta and weight analysis. The mixed-methods approach was defined with developmental purpose, with the qualitative findings feeding the development of the consumer research model. The qualitative study targeted several stakeholders, while the quantitative one only targeted consumers. The data collection on the first study was done through semi-structured interviews, while the second was performed with an online questionnaire with mostly questions in a numerical scale from 1 to 7. Most analyses performed were therefore with cross-sectional data. For the data analysis, an open coding methodology was used for the qualitative study, while the partial least squares technique was the chosen one for the quantitative research.
- **Step 3: Interpret – Key results** – this step aims to interpret the achieved results, i.e., making sure the results are aligned or not with the expected and if they answered the proposed objectives in Step 1. Specifically to our project, the main results highlight the importance of user interaction with the technology, empowerment as the most critical factor influencing citizens participation in LFMs, no major differences were found between countries, however a cross-country analysis should always be performed. Finally a longitudinal validation was developed, measuring the outcomes of the participation in a second moment of time, validating the strong and positive benefits of LFMs in both community and individual dimensions. Based on all these, we were able to meet the established objectives, i.e., identify the most relevant factors influencing consumers participation and the perceived impact in a set of outcomes (in this case, measured 2 years later, as recommended by literature).
- **Step 4: Act – Practical recommendations** – the final step is to develop practical recommendations based on the data analysis results. Here, a set of lessons learned and best practices can be developed.

Lessons learned

Specifically to the DE-RISK project, four main action points are highlighted:

- ⇒ **The importance of technology design** - offer multiple entry points and functions (e.g., data dashboards, discussion forums, local polls); Prioritize user-friendly, multilingual, and mobile-compatible platforms. **Enjoyment**, compared to usefulness of platforms had a surprising effect, calling attention to the design and engagement features of the technologies that should provide an enjoyable/fun user experience;
- ⇒ **Provide on-going stimuli** - go beyond initial engagement (e.g., challenges, learning content, rewards) to sustain participation over time. Continuous messaging, especially focused on **coping strategies** than threats ones should be developed;
- ⇒ **Measure continuously** – if possible use **longitudinal tracking** to evaluate behavioral trends, satisfaction, and evolving needs, not just static outcomes.
- ⇒ **Provide continuous (diversified) feedback** – project evaluation outcomes should always be provided to the customers, both individual and community wise. Most importantly, this feedback should not only contain technical and practical measures but also more **human-centered impacts**, such as comfort or well-being. Even though more difficult to measure (this project adopted a questionnaire-based strategy), these should be provided to users, and decision makers, to better **comprehend the technical and human outcomes** of the proposed solutions.

G. KEY LIMITATIONS

This chapter summarizes the main limitations and constraints found during the consumer behavior analysis. Limitations are as follows:

- **Complexity of the consumer behavior** - Consumer journeys in local flexibility markets involve multiple touchpoints and decision factors (e.g., economic incentives, technology adoption, environmental awareness). Capturing the full complexity of behavior can be challenging and may oversimplify actual consumer motivations and barriers.
- **Data availability and quality** - The methodology relies on data from surveys and interviews. Especially to evaluate use outcomes, logs and analytical data could be useful to better measure the interaction of the user.
- **Dynamic market conditions** - Local flexibility markets are rapidly evolving with new technologies, regulations, and participants. The consumer journey framework may not fully account for fast-changing conditions or emerging trends, making insights less predictive over time.
- **Heterogeneity of consumers** - Consumers differ widely in energy needs, preferences, and technological literacy. The framework may struggle to represent diverse segments accurately, leading to generalizations that miss key niche behaviors or barriers.
- **Limited scope on external factors** - External influences such as regulatory changes, grid constraints, or macroeconomic shifts can significantly affect consumer choices but may be underrepresented in the consumer journey analysis.
- **Focus on individual consumers** - Local flexibility markets often involve interactions between multiple stakeholders (e.g., aggregators, utilities, prosumers). The consumer journey methodology typically centers on the end-user perspective, potentially neglecting system-level dynamics and interactions, even though interviews with different stakeholders were performed.
- **Implementation and scalability challenges** - Applying detailed consumer journey analysis requires time and resources, which can be difficult for smaller market players or regulators. Additionally, scaling insights from local pilots to broader regions may not always be straightforward.

Therefore, the consumer behavior journey framework should be seen as complementary to other already implemented analysis (e.g. market analysis, SWOT analysis, PESTLE analysis, among others).

H. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has synthesized the consumer behavior change journey within the context of local flexibility markets, combining theoretical insights and empirical evidence collected across multiple countries and stakeholder groups. Through an integrated methodological approach, this work has mapped the drivers, barriers, and dynamics of citizen engagement in decentralized energy systems. The framework and insights developed offer both an analytical lens and a strategic tool for designing more inclusive, effective, and responsive energy programs.

Beyond academic contribution, the findings serve a deeply practical purpose. They provide a replicable roadmap for future LFM deployments, focusing on the citizen engagement perspective. Moreover, longitudinal insights underscored the need to evaluate not just static behaviors, but evolving user experiences and outcomes such as perceived well-being and environmental impact.

Specifically for the project, four key action points emerge: (1) prioritize technology design that is user-friendly, accessible, and engaging; (2) implement continuous engagement strategies to maintain long-term involvement, focused on coping and not threat messaging; (3) adopt longitudinal measurement tools to monitor change over time; and (4) provide continuous, diversified feedback to users, highlighting both technical results and human-centered outcomes. These lessons learned are not only applicable to the DE-RISK pilots but offer transferable best practices for broader energy transition initiatives. By placing citizens at the heart of flexibility markets, this deliverable charts a path toward energy systems that are not only decentralized, but also participatory and sustainable.

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Appendix A - Questionnaire

Turkish questionnaire

Use behaviour (reflective)	Kullanım davranışı (yansıtıcı)
I often use sustainable technologies in my household.	Evimde sıklıkla sürdürülebilir teknolojileri kullanırım
I often use sustainable technologies to manage my energy consumption.	Enerji tüketimimi yönetmek için genellikle sürdürülebilir teknolojileri kullanırım
I often use sustainable technologies to monitor my energy consumption	Enerji tüketimimi izlemek için genellikle sürdürülebilir teknolojileri kullanırım
Use (formative) - On a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means Never and 7 Many times, please choose your usage frequency for each of the following:	Kullanım (biçimlendirici) - Lütfen aşağıdakilerden her biri için 1'den 7'ye kadar, 1'in "Hiçbir Zaman" ve 7'nin "Çoğu kez" anlamına geldiği bir ölçekte kullanım sıklığınızı seçiniz:
IoT wearable devices (e.g. smart watches)	IoT giyilebilir cihazlar (ör. akıllı saatler)
IoT smart home devices (e.g. smart meters, smart plugs)	IoT akıllı ev cihazları (ör. akıllı sayaçlar, akıllı prizler)
Renewable energy sources (RES) (e.g. solar panels)	Yenilenebilir enerji kaynakları (RES) (örn. güneş panelleri)
Electric vehicle	Elektrikli araç
Smart thermostats	Akıllı termostatlar
Participation in local energy communities	Yerel Enerji Topluluklarına Katılım
I intend to become part of the local energy community in the next months	Önümüzdeki aylarda yerel enerji topluluğunun bir parçası olmayı amaçlıyorum
I predict I will become part of the local energy community in the next months	Önümüzdeki aylarda yerel enerji topluluğunun bir parçası olacağımı tahmin ediyorum
I plan to become part of the local energy community in the next months	Önümüzdeki aylarda yerel enerji topluluğunun bir parçası olmayı planlıyorum
Perceived well-being (local energy communities)	Algılanan refah (yerel enerji toplulukları)
Overall, participating in the local energy community has satisfied my overall household needs	Genel olarak, yerel enerji topluluğuna katılmak genel hane ihtiyaçlarımı karşıladı
Overall, participating in the local energy community has played a very important role in my social well-being	Genel olarak, yerel enerji topluluğuna katılmak sosyal refahımda çok önemli bir rol oynadı
Overall, participating in the local energy community has played a very important role in my leisure well-being	Genel olarak, yerel enerji topluluğuna katılmak, boş zamanlarımdaki esenliğimde çok önemli bir rol oynadı
Overall, participating in the local energy community has played an important role in enhancing the quality of life in my household	Genel olarak, yerel enerji topluluğuna katılmak, hanemdeki yaşam kalitesini artırmada önemli bir rol oynadı.
Community environmental performance	
My local energy community is focused to reduce hazardous waste.	Yerel enerji topluluğum tehlikeli atıkları azaltmaya odaklanıyor.
My local energy community is focused to consume fewer natural resources.	Yerel enerji topluluğum daha az doğal kaynak tüketmeye odaklanıyor.
My local energy community is interested to comply with environmental regulation.	Yerel enerji topluluğum çevre mevzuatına uyuma odaklanıyor.
My local energy community is generating societal benefits.	Yerel enerji topluluğum toplumsal fayda sağlıyor.
Energy poverty alleviation	
Local energy communities reduce health issues at the household level.	Yerel enerji toplulukları, hane düzeyinde sağlık sorunlarını azaltır.
Local energy communities provide the opportunity for energy-efficient consumption in rural areas.	Yerel enerji toplulukları kırsal alanlarda enerji verimli tüketim fırsatı sunar.
Local energy communities create jobs opportunity.	Yerel enerji toplulukları istihdam fırsatları yaratır.
Alleviation of energy poverty is necessary to promote local energy communities.	Enerji yoksulluğunun azaltılması, yerel enerji topluluklarını teşvik edilmesi için gereklidir.

Spanish questionnaire

Use behaviour (reflective)	Comportamiento de uso (reflexivo)
I often use sustainable technologies in my household.	A menudo uso tecnologías sostenibles en mi hogar.
I often use sustainable technologies to manage my energy consumption.	A menudo utilizo tecnologías sostenibles para gestionar mi consumo de energía.
I often use sustainable technologies to monitor my energy consumption	A menudo utilizo tecnologías sostenibles para controlar mi consumo de energía.
Use (formative) - On a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means Never and 7 Many times, please choose your usage frequency for each of the following:	Uso (formativo): en una escala del 1 al 7, donde 1 significa Nunca y 7 Muchas veces, elija su frecuencia de uso para cada uno de los siguientes:
IoT wearable devices (e.g. smart watches)	Dispositivos vestibles IoT (por ejemplo, relojes inteligentes)
IoT smart home devices (e.g. smart meters, smart plugs)	Dispositivos domésticos inteligentes IoT (por ejemplo, medidores inteligentes, enchufes inteligentes)
Renewable energy sources (RES) (e.g. solar panels)	Fuentes de energía renovable (RES) (por ejemplo, paneles solares)
Electric vehicle	Vehículo eléctrico
Smart thermostats	Termostatos inteligentes
On a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means Strongly disagree and 7 Strongly agree, please evaluate the following statements:	En una escala del 1 al 7, donde 1 significa Totalmente en desacuerdo y 7 Totalmente de acuerdo, evalúe las siguientes afirmaciones:
Participation in local energy communities	Participación en comunidades energéticas locales
I intend to become part of the local energy community in the next months	Tengo la intención de formar parte de la comunidad energética local en los próximos meses.
I predict I will become part of the local energy community in the next months	Predigo que me convertiré en parte de la comunidad energética local en los próximos meses.
I plan to become part of the local energy community in the next months	Planeo convertirme en parte de la comunidad energética local en los próximos meses.
Perceived well-being (local energy communities)	Bienestar percibido (comunidades energéticas locales)
Overall, participating in the local energy community has satisfied my overall household needs	En general, participar en la comunidad energética local com satisfecho las necesidades generales de mi hogar
Overall, participating in the local energy community has played a very important role in my social well-being	En general, participar en la comunidad energética local com jugado un papel muy importante en mi bienestar social.
Overall, participating in the local energy community has played a very important role in my leisure well-being	En general, participar en la comunidad energética local com jugado un papel muy importante en mi bienestar de ocio.
Overall, participating in the local energy community has played an important role in enhancing the quality of life in my household	En general, participar en la comunidad energética local com jugado un papel importante en la mejora de la calidad de vida en mi hogar.
Community environmental performance	
My local energy community is focused to reduce hazardous waste.	Mi comunidad energética local está enfocada en reducir los desechos peligrosos.
My local energy community is focused to consume fewer natural resources.	Mi comunidad energética local está enfocada en consumir menos recursos naturales.
My local energy community is interested to comply with environmental regulation.	Mi comunidad energética local está interesada en cumplir con las regulaciones ambientales.
Energy poverty alleviation	
My local energy community is generating societal benefits.	Mi comunidad energética local está generando beneficios sociales.
Local energy communities reduce health issues at the household level.	Las comunidades energéticas locales reducen los problemas de salud a nivel doméstico.

Local energy communities provide the opportunity for energy-efficient consumption in rural areas.	Las comunidades energéticas locales brindan la oportunidad de un consumo eficiente de energía en áreas rurales.
Local energy communities create jobs opportunity.	Las comunidades energéticas locales crean oportunidades de empleo.
Alleviation of energy poverty is necessary to promote local energy communities.	La reducción de la pobreza energética es necesaria para promover las comunidades energéticas locales.

Portuguese questionnaire

Use behaviour (reflective)	Hábitos de uso/consumo (refletivo)
I often use sustainable technologies in my household.	Usualmente uso tecnologias sustentáveis na minha casa
I often use sustainable technologies to manage my energy consumption.	Usualmente uso tecnologias sustentáveis para gerir o meu consumo energético
I often use sustainable technologies to monitor my energy consumption	Usualmente uso tecnologias sustentáveis para controlar o meu consumo energético
Use (formative) - On a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means Never and 7 Many times, please choose your usage frequency for each of the following:	Uso (formativo) - Numa escala de 1 a 7 onde 1 significa Nunca e 7 Muitas vezes, por favor escolha a frequência de uso para cada um dos seguintes:
IoT wearable devices (e.g. smart watches)	Dispositivos vestíveis inteligentes (ex. relógios inteligentes)
IoT smart home devices (e.g. smart meters, smart plugs)	Dispositivos de casa inteligentes (ex. contadores inteligentes, tomadas inteligentes)
Renewable energy sources (RES) (e.g. solar panels)	Fontes de energia renováveis (ex. painéis solares)
Electric vehicle	Veículo elétrico
Smart thermostats	Termostatos inteligentes
Participation in local energy communities	Participação em comunidades locais de energia
I intend to become part of the local energy community in the next months	Eu pretendo tornar-me parte de uma comunidade local de energia nos próximos meses
I predict I will become part of the local energy community in the next months	Eu prevejo fazer parte de uma comunidade local de energia nos próximos meses
I plan to become part of the local energy community in the next months	Eu planeio tornar-me parte de uma comunidade local de energia nos próximos meses
Community environmental performance	
My local energy community is focused to reduce hazardous waste.	A minha comunidade de energia local está focada em reduzir resíduos perigosos.
My local energy community is focused to consume fewer natural resources.	A minha comunidade de energia local está focada em consumir menos recursos naturais.
My local energy community is interested to comply with environmental regulation.	A minha comunidade de energia local está interessada em cumprir a regulamentação ambiental.
My local energy community is generating societal benefits.	A minha comunidade de energia local está a gerar benefícios sociais.
Energy poverty alleviation	
Local energy communities reduce health issues at the household level.	As comunidades de energia locais reduzem problemas de saúde ao nível doméstico.
Local energy communities provide the opportunity for energy-efficient consumption in rural areas.	As comunidades de energia locais oferecem a oportunidade de um consumo energético mais eficiente em áreas rurais.
Local energy communities create jobs opportunity.	As comunidades de energia locais criam oportunidades de emprego.
Alleviation of energy poverty is necessary to promote local energy communities.	A redução da pobreza energética é necessária para promover as comunidades de energia locais.

French questionnaire

Use behaviour (reflective)	
I often use sustainable technologies in my household.	J'utilise souvent des technologies durables dans mon ménage.
I often use sustainable technologies to manage my energy consumption.	J'utilise souvent des technologies durables pour gérer ma consommation d'énergie.
I often use sustainable technologies to monitor my energy consumption	J'utilise souvent des technologies durables pour surveiller ma consommation d'énergie
Use (formative) - On a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means Never and 7 Many times, please choose your usage frequency for each of the following:	Utilisation (formative) - Sur une échelle de 1 à 7, où 1 signifie Jamais et 7 Plusieurs fois, veuillez choisir votre fréquence d'utilisation pour chacun des éléments suivants :
IoT wearable devices (e.g. smart watches)	Appareils portables IdO (p. ex. montres intelligentes)
IoT smart home devices (e.g. smart meters, smart plugs)	Appareils domestiques intelligents IdO (p. ex. compteurs intelligents, prises intelligentes)
Renewable energy sources (RES) (e.g. solar panels)	Sources d'énergie renouvelables (SER) (p. ex. panneaux solaires)
Electric vehicle	Véhicule électrique
Smart thermostats	Thermostats intelligents
Participation in local energy communities	Participation aux communautés énergétiques locales
I intend to become part of the local energy community in the next months	J'ai l'intention de faire partie de la communauté énergétique locale dans les prochains mois
I predict I will become part of the local energy community in the next months	Je prévois que je ferai partie de la communauté énergétique locale dans les prochains mois
I plan to become part of the local energy community in the next months	Je prévois de faire partie de la communauté énergétique locale dans les prochains mois
Perceived well-being (local energy communities)	Bien-être perçu (communautés énergétiques locales)
Overall, participating in the local energy community has satisfied my overall household needs	Dans l'ensemble, ma participation à la communauté énergétique locale a satisfait les besoins généraux de mon ménage
Overall, participating in the local energy community has played a very important role in my social well-being	Dans l'ensemble, participer à la communauté énergétique locale a joué un rôle très important dans mon bien-être social
Overall, participating in the local energy community has played a very important role in my leisure well-being	Dans l'ensemble, participer à la communauté énergétique locale a joué un rôle très important dans mon bien-être de loisirs
Overall, participating in the local energy community has played an important role in enhancing the quality of life in my household	Dans l'ensemble, la participation à la communauté énergétique locale a joué un rôle important dans l'amélioration de la qualité de vie dans mon ménage
Community environmental performance	
My local energy community is focused to reduce hazardous waste.	Ma communauté énergétique locale est axée sur la réduction des déchets dangereux.
My local energy community is focused to consume fewer natural resources.	Ma communauté énergétique locale est axée sur la réduction de la consommation de ressources naturelles.
My local energy community is interested to comply with environmental regulation.	Ma communauté énergétique locale s'intéresse au respect de la réglementation environnementale.

Energy poverty alleviation	
My local energy community is generating societal benefits.	Les communautés énergétiques locales réduisent les problèmes de santé au niveau des ménages.
Local energy communities reduce health issues at the household level.	Les communautés énergétiques locales offrent la possibilité d'une consommation énergétique plus efficace dans les zones rurales.
Local energy communities provide the opportunity for energy-efficient consumption in rural areas.	Les communautés énergétiques locales créent des opportunités d'emploi.
Local energy communities create jobs opportunity.	La réduction de la précarité énergétique est nécessaire pour promouvoir les communautés énergétiques locales.
Alleviation of energy poverty is necessary to promote local energy communities.	Les communautés énergétiques locales réduisent les problèmes de santé au niveau des ménages.

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